

FORMATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF FIBRE-MATRIX INTERFACES IN CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED SILICON CARBIDE

Pamela M. Farries and Jean-Bernard Veyret

*European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Institute for Advanced Materials,
PO Box 2, 1755 ZG Petten, The Netherlands.*

SUMMARY: The effect of processing conditions on interface formation in a fibre reinforced silicon carbide composite was investigated through infiltration of a uni-directional lay-up of pitch-based carbon fibres with an aqueous ceramic powder suspension and subsequent consolidation at high temperature. Interface formation by a conventional method - the attempted preservation of a pyrolytic carbon coating applied to the fibres by CVD - is contrasted to an *in-situ* method, involving the exploitation of the migration of yttria (included with the SiC powder along with alumina as sintering aids) to the fibre-matrix interface by hot-pressing at temperatures of 1750 and 1800°C in an ambient argon atmosphere and sintering without mechanical pressure at 1850°C in an argon atmosphere. Basic indications of mechanical properties determined from 4-point bending tests at room temperature are included. Early indications are that fibre degradation is inhibited in hot-pressing producing an interface which can debond.

KEYWORDS: silicon carbide, interfaces, fibres, liquid phase sintering, hot-pressing, YAG (yttrium aluminium garnet)

INTRODUCTION

Commissioning of long fibre reinforced ceramics into industrial service is becoming an achievable goal as properties are improved to meet target requirements, but this success simultaneously shifts emphasis for improvement towards the cost of producing a composite of consistent high quality. Consolidation methods without applied mechanical pressure are being investigated, however, process development is still constrained by the need to create or preserve a pre-designed fibre-matrix interface architecture, often generated by complex and expensive fibre coatings, during the very high temperature consolidation cycle. These two constraints are inextricably linked and serious process developments can be made only by considering the implications to interface structure and chemistry throughout production and service.

Carbon and boron nitride are the most common choices of material which satisfy the required criteria for debonding and controlled sliding at the fibre/matrix interface of silicon carbide based CMC's, so imparting a degree of toughness to a material comprising two brittle components. Both C and BN are susceptible to oxidation and in systems using SiC fibres, the gap left by the removal of the interphase is filled by a silicate layer produced from the oxidation of the fibre which does not satisfy the debonding and sliding requirements [1]. This is unfortunate when the layer was produced *in-situ* during composite production, such as in

the case of Nicalon reinforced lithium aluminium silicate (LAS) glass, but is a much more serious concern when the interface was deliberately deposited. The move towards oxide-oxide composite systems has prompted investigation of porous oxide and refractory metal coatings [2]. Sputter deposited yttria coatings have been utilised in metal matrix composites to protect SiC monofilaments from reaction with an Mg-Li alloy[3]. Combining the metal matrix and oxide-oxide composite experience with the observations that alumina and yttria sintering aids in silicon carbide have a propensity to migrate to free surfaces at high temperatures [4-7] and alumina is observed to evaporate at high processing temperatures [4,6] presents the possibility of a novel mechanism for the production of a compatible oxide interface during the processing and use of a SiC/SiC composite which may be investigated in tandem with existing methods [8].

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The conditions necessary for production of a silicon carbide matrix composite, reinforced with pitch-based carbon fibre by infiltration of a uni-directional lay-up with an aqueous ceramic powder suspension containing silicon carbide and the liquid phase forming additives alumina and yttria, and consolidation by hot-pressing are investigated, with the eventual aim of including Hi-Nicalon silicon carbide fibre. The interfaces produced when composite samples are densified with and without the application of mechanical pressure are compared through EDX analysis and a first indication of mechanical properties obtained from four point bending. Background to the chemical and physical development of the interface during processing is provided from the results of an extensive study into the effects of varying alumina and yttria additive concentration, sintering temperature, hold time and sintering environment on the density, microstructure and chemical composition of free sintered silicon carbide [8]. The effect of these sintering variables on free sintered tows of un-coated and pyrolytic carbon coated carbon fibres are also detailed.

Sample Preparation

Monolithic silicon carbide samples were prepared from α -SiC powder with a mean particle diameter of 0.6 μ m - UF-15 from H.C. Starck - by pressure filtration of an aqueous powder suspension (optimised at 47vol% powder using information obtained with Matec™ Applied Sciences, Electrokinetic Sonic Analysis System) dispersed using an ultrasonic probe. Alumina (Baco RA 207LS Grade) and yttria (H.C. Starck Fine Grade) were added in the 3:5 (alumina:yttria) YAG molar ratio and their combined mass was either 3 or 9wt% of the total powder, Table 1. Amoco P25 pitch based carbon fibre was dipped as tows into the slurries used for monolith production and wound as 1D lay ups for composite casting from a slurry of composition B containing a reduced volume of solids (40%) and a small amount of wetting agent to allow complete infiltration.

Table 1: Sample compositions and theoretical densities (TD)

Composition	Sintering aid content (Al ₂ O ₃ +Y ₂ O ₃) wt%	Molar % Y ₂ O ₃ in mix	Theoretical Density g/cm ³ (rule of mixtures)
A	9	62.5	3.30
B	3	62.5	3.24

Densification

Composite samples were hot-pressed at 1750 and 1800°C in an ambient argon atmosphere. Mechanical pressure of 27MPa was applied incrementally beginning when the temperature reached 1500°C and reaching its maximum at the peak sintering temperature. Thereafter both temperature and pressure were maintained at maximum for 60 minutes. Heating and cooling temperature ramps were set at 10°/min.

Pressureless sintering was carried out in a graphite resistance furnace at temperatures between 1750 and 1900°C under 10bar argon pressure for hold times of up to 120 minutes in a closed graphite crucible. Sample-crucible contact was prevented by the use of the minimum amount of coarse SiC powder required, except in the case where and sinter bed containing 1.33wt% alumina (indicated in Table 2) was used.

Table 2: Pressureless densification conditions

Temperature (°C) Hold Time (mins)	1750	1800	1850	1900
30			A, B, fibre+B	
60			A, B, Composite	
120	A, B	A, B, fibre+A	A, B, fibre+A, fibre+B, coated fibre+B	A, B, fibre+A, fibre+B, coated fibre+B
120 alumina bed			A, B	

Analysis

Monolithic samples were subjected to phase analysis by X-ray diffraction (XRD), aluminium and yttrium content analysis by atomic absorption spectroscopy and density measurement by mercury immersion. Linear shrinkage and mass loss during sintering were also determined for these samples. All samples were examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and the composite hot-pressed at the lower temperature tested in 4-point bending.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Monolithic Silicon Carbide Densification

The peak density achieved when sintering without a sinter bed was 2.97g/cm³ or 90% of the theoretical density (TD) for samples of composition A sintered at 1900°C. The samples sintered for 120 minutes all showed a markedly improved final density figure when sintered at temperatures above 1850°C, when shrinkage values were correspondingly greater, as too were mass loss figures. Atomic absorption spectroscopy revealed, however, that up to half of the

aluminium originally added was being lost from the samples of composition A sintered at 1900°C along with approximately 20% of the yttrium [8], this observation being backed up by the detection of an yttria rich phase in XRD ($2Y_2O_3:Al_2O_3$ as opposed to the expected YAG phase $3Y_2O_3:5Al_2O_3$) indicating that a shift in the composition of the liquid phase had occurred. The holding time at peak temperature was reduced in an attempt to minimise alumina volatilisation and mass loss, Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Density variation of monolithic SiC with hold time at 1850°C

Trends projected from sintering carried out at 1850°C for 30, 60 and 120 minutes, suggested that the maximum density for composition A would be achieved at this temperature from a high temperature hold of 45 to 60 minutes in length, while for composition B the optimum soak time is around 90 minutes. Prolonged holds are damaging for both compositions. The increased density drop for the samples containing larger amounts of alumina (and hence having the capacity to lose a larger proportion of their mass) held for 120 minutes at high temperature proves the influence of time on alumina volatilisation. Mass losses are reduced significantly with a sintering hold time of 30 minutes but densification is no longer satisfactory.

Addition of 1.33wt% alumina to a sinter bed of coarse silicon carbide resulted in the highest density figure achieved - 92.4% TD for a sample of composition A for a two hour hold at 1850°C. Calculating the density increase as a percentage of the original green density of the sample provides a convenient method for monitoring densification efficiency under different conditions, while neutralising the effect of any variation in green density, Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Effect of alumina on densification efficiency at a sintering temperature of 1850°C

As also demonstrated in Fig. 1, a hold time of 60 minutes at temperature produces a greater density increase than a 120 minute hold, Fig. 2, the effect being especially noticeable for samples containing 9wt% which under these circumstances achieve a smaller density increase than samples containing 3wt% additives, again demonstrating the volatility of the sintering additions. This order is reversed when a sinter bed containing alumina surrounds the samples, presumably preventing the evaporation of alumina and emission of carbon dioxide produced on its reaction with SiC [5], and allowing the full benefit of an increased volume of liquid phase to be realised.

Microstructural Observations

Monolithic Silicon Carbide

Silicon carbide was seen to densify leaving only isolated porosity at temperatures of 1850°C and above where the hold time was at least 60 minutes. Samples of composition B sintered for a shorter time or at lower temperature were dense only in a region extending 0.5mm from the surface (overall dimensions, 15 x 15 x 5 mm) seeming to indicate densification occurring from outside inward. When viewed in back scattered mode, the 1850 and 1900°C samples sintered for 120 minutes show an unusual distribution of light contrast areas, Fig 3(a), shown to be rich in yttrium through Energy Dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX), the contrast effect being associated with yttrium's high atomic number. The central zone at the top of the micrograph contains a few widely spaced areas of the yttrium rich material up to 100µm in length. The outer zone contains a more even dispersion of small areas rich in yttrium. The effect was not seen for any composition A samples sintered at temperatures lower than 1850°C, for a hold time shorter than 120 minutes or for any of the composition B samples. Combination of these observations suggest that densification occurs from the surface to the centre and when the hold time is long enough and temperature high enough, the excess of a high yttrium content second phase begins to segregate out, possibly to flaws and grain boundaries.

Figure 3: (a) SiC monolith containing 9wt% alumina and yttria in the YAG ratio sintered for 120 minutes at 1850°C (b) Carbon coated fibre and SiC+3wt% YAG sintered for 120 minutes at 1850°C

Examination of samples sintered in an alumina containing bed at 1850°C showed microstructures similar to those sintered without bedding powder at 1950°C but without the light contrast areas of yttria rich material.

Fibre Tows

Of the fibre tows sintered alongside the monolithic samples, the carbon coated fibre showed the most interesting behaviour. Tows dipped in slurry of composition B and sintered for 120 minutes at 1850°C did not appear to be badly damaged and the area previously occupied by the pyrolytic carbon coating is now filled with an yttrium rich phase, Fig. 3(b). Uncoated fibres sintered under the same conditions were slightly degraded by the matrix Carbon coated fibre dipped in slurry containing 9wt% additives showed yttrium ingress well into the body of the fibre [8]. Fig. 3(b) appears to illustrate that at lower temperatures and with less oxide additives the pyrolytic carbon layer is consumed sacrificially and the an yttrium rich interphase subsequently forms.

Composite Properties

Composite green bodies were manufactured with a fibre volume fraction designed to rise to 35% on densification of the matrix. Initial hot-pressing at 1750°C, judged to be the lower temperature limit for feasible densification of the matrix and coinciding with the lowest temperature applied in the pressureless sintering study, produced a composite with only 80% TD and a correspondingly low volume fraction of fibres - 27vol%. This was reflected in the mechanical properties of the material, the failure stress reaching a maximum of 200MPa in 4-point bending. Sonic resonance measurements however indicated a Young's modulus of around 170GPa, not significantly lower than the value predicted by the rule of mixtures. Hot-pressing at 1800°C produced a composite of 98% TD which has yet to be analysed.

Examination of the fracture surfaces of the bend tested material hot-pressed at 1750°C and cross-sections of this and a similarly prepared green body sintered with out pressure

application at 1850°C in a 10 bar argon atmosphere, give reason for optimism regarding interface formation, even with this uncoated fibre.

Figure 4: Fibre pull-out on 4-point bend specimen - un-coated P25 fibre, hot-pressed at 1750°C, 3wt% sintering additives

Clean fibre surfaces pulled up to 150µm out of the fibre surface are shown in figure 4 indicating surprisingly little fibre damage. Cross sections prepared to allow analysis of the fibre matrix interface confirm the assertion.

Figure 5: (a) Longitudinal section of material hot-pressed at 1750°C (b) Cross section of composite free sintered at 1850°C, both reinforced with un-coated fibre

EDX spot analysis on the cross section shown in Fig 5(a) showed no significant trace of silicon in the fibre centre, indicating that the fibres are being protected from reaction with the oxide additives by the high pressure exerted during hot-pressing. No significant concentrations of alumina or yttria were observed in the sample. The matrix of the free sintered sample (Fig. 5(b)) is much more porous than that of the hot-pressed sample, but the fibres still retain complete integrity of form even at the very high processing temperature and without the benefit of applied mechanical pressure to inhibit reactions. A stronger silicon signal is detected in these fibres but the presence of a significant carbon peak indicates that the phase is far from SiC in composition. When carbon and silicon are present in equal quantities the strong silicon signal swamps the peak due to carbon. The darker amorphous annulus visible around these fibres is found to be rich in yttrium and to contain some aluminium.

CONCLUSIONS

Pressureless liquid phase sintering of silicon carbide with additions of Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 was carried out successfully at temperatures at and above 1850°C . Placing samples in an alumina containing silicon carbide sinter bed further improved densification and inhibited the loss of alumina from the sample and migration of the liquid phase.

The application of mechanical pressure did not lower the temperature required for SiC densification as far as expected, but processing at 1750°C did produce a composite with a fibre matrix interface capable of debonding.

Yttria rich material is seen at the fibre matrix interface in composites densified by pressureless means, but this migration appears to be hindered by the application of mechanical pressure in hot-pressing.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was carried out under the Fourth Framework Programme of the European Commission and the principal author is grateful to The European Commission for the provision of a fellowship under the Human Capital and Mobility Programme.

REFERENCES

1. Thouless, M.D., Sbaizero, O. and Evans, A.G., "Effect of Interface Mechanical Properties on Pullout in a SiC-Fiber-Reinforced Lithium Aluminium Silicate Glass-Ceramic", *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 72, No. 4, 1989, pp.525-32.
2. Davis, J.B., Löfvander, J.P.A. and Evans, A.G., "Fiber Coating Concepts for Brittle-Matrix Composites", *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 76, No. 5, 1995, pp.1249-57.
3. Kieschke, R.R., Warwick, C.M. and Clyne, T.W., "Sputter Deposited Barrier Coatings on SiC Monofilaments for use in Reactive Metal Matrices - III. Microstructural Stability in Composites Based on Magnesium and Titanium", *Acta. metallurgica et materialia*, Vol. 39, No. 4, 1991, pp.445-452.
4. Kerber, A. and Velken, S.V., "Liquid Phase Sintered Silicon Carbide: Production Properties and Possible Applications", *Proceedings of the Fourth European Ceramic Society Conference*, Riccione, Italy, October 2-6, 1995, Vol. 2: Developments in Processing of Advanced Ceramics - II, Galassi, C., Ed, pp.177-184.
5. Mulla, M.A. and Krstic V.D., "Low-Temperature Pressureless Sintering of β -Silicon Carbide with Aluminium Oxide and Yttrium Oxide Additions", *Ceramic Bulletin*, Vol. 70, No. 3, 1991, pp.439-442.
6. Kahlman, L., Rundgren, K., Lidén, E., Nyberg, B. and Calström. E., "Processing of Liquid Phase Sintered SiC - Mechanical and Wear Properties", *Proceedings of the Third European Ceramic Society Conference*, Madrid, Spain, September 12-17, 1993, Vol. 3: Engineering Ceramics, Duran, P. and Fernandez, J.F., Eds., pp.477-482.
7. Kostic, E., "Sintering of Silicon Carbide in the Presence of Oxide Additives" *Powder Metallurgy International*, Vol. 20, No. 6, 1988, pp.28-29.
8. Farries, P.M., Veyret, J-B. and Rawlings, R.D., "Fibre Reinforced Silicon Carbide: Effect of Densification Method and Parameters", *Key Engineering Materials*, Vols. 127-131, 1997, pp.295-302.